

Activities of the DEMIX Subgroup 3 "Platforms and Processing"

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Abstract—In recent years, an important number of global Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) have been released publicly, with very permissive licenses. Although beneficial to the scientific field, this profusion of data makes it difficult to choose the most adequate DEM for a given field of application. Since 2020, DEM assessment and comparison methodologies have been standardised under the frameworks of the Earthnet Data Assessment Project (EDAP / EDAP+) led by the European Space Agency (ESA), and the DEM Intercomparison eXercise (DEMIX) initiated by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS). EDAP evaluation guidelines provide a comprehensive set of criteria to assess Earth Observation (EO) missions and products based on their documentation. While initially conceived for missions, these standard guidelines were adapted to the case of DEM products. On the other hand, the DEMIX methodology, based on the Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD), allows users to rank DEMs according to user-defined areas of interest and criteria. Jointly used, these frameworks give scientists a complete analysis of DEM products, from overall assessments to very specific user criteria. While these evaluation standards are mature, fundamental DEM activities are still performed under EDAP and DEMIX. Most of these works are carried-out and discussed in the DEMIX Subgroup 3 (SG3) called “Platforms and processing”. Since the beginning of DEMIX, this subgroup carried out global DEM quality assessments using spaceborne LiDAR data, DEM planimetric misregistration assessments, extended DEM transformation studies including resampling methods, reprojections and datum changes, and analyses of open local VHR DEMs. The knowledge gained from these studies has been used to develop free DEM visualisation and processing web applications, including VtWeb, QGIS tools, a DEMIX Jupyter Notebook, the DEMIX Operations Platform and DEM4Sentinels-1-2. Thanks to these free tools, public users are now able to visualise and process DEMs in an easy interactive way.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a digital representation of elevations (or height) of a topographic surface in form of a georectified point-based or area-based grid, covering the Earth or other solid celestial bodies [1]. Numerous of these models are now publicly available, with various spatial coverages (city, state, country; continental or global) and temporal extents (several days to more than a decade). The most popular public DEMs are global and generated at a Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of 1'' arcsecond (e.g., ALOS World 3D, ASTER GDEM, Copernicus DEM GLO-30, SRTM). These models are the result of a complex processing chain, usually involving a main (or primary) source of elevations processed from Earth Observation (EO) acquisitions (radar interferometry, optical photogrammetry or LiDAR aggregation). Due to instrument limitations or to insufficient qualified observations, DEM products may present voids, be edited (interpolations, lake flattening...) or filled with external sources of elevations. These characteristics complicate the choice of the “best” DEM for a given application, as it is dependent on a wide variety of parameters and criteria. Fortunately, two complementary frameworks allow the evaluation of DEM products: the EDAP project, led by ESA, and DEMIX, initiated by the CEOS. These two frameworks respectively allow to perform overall product maturity assessments and user-defined tests specific to the field(s) of study and area(s) of interest. Both projects have benefited from each other and are still jointly evolving thanks to the financing of the DEMIX Subgroup 3 (SG3) “Platform and Processing” activities through EDAP. The current paper aims to summarize the main achievements and future works of DEMIX SG3, from the contributions to EDAP quality assessment guidelines to the DEM transformation studies (resampling, datum

and projection changes) and the development of free DEM processing and visualisation tools (VtWeb, the DEMIX Operations Platform, the DEMIX Jupyter Notebook and DEM4Sentinels-1-2). Section II presents the EDAP project and quality assessment guidelines. Section III presents DEMIX and its subgroups. Section IV focuses on the works of DEMIX Subgroup 3 (SG3), dedicated to platforms and processing.

II. THE EARTHNET DATA ASSESSMENT PROJECT (EDAP)

The EDAP project (2018-2021) and its successor EDAP+ (since 2022) are responsible for assessing the quality and suitability of candidate missions being considered for ESA’s Earthnet Programme as Third-Party Missions (TPM) [2]. This includes optical, Synthetic-aperture radar (SAR), atmospheric, Automatic Identification System (AIS) and Radio Frequency (RF) missions, multi-mission studies and DEM assessments. EDAP assessments are performed with regards to evaluation guidelines available in generic and mission (or product) specific versions [3]. These guidelines cover the entire chain of processing, from the instrument calibrations to the generation of EO products. Following these guidelines, the overall maturity of an EO mission and its derived product(s) can be precisely assessed. Naturally, users can also be interested by the “fitness for purpose” of a given product to their specific application. For the case of DEMs, quality assessment and ranking methodologies developed by the DEMIX community are perfectly suitable for this purpose.

III. THE DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL INTERCOMPARISON EXERCISE (DEMIX)

The DEMIX working group is a CEOS initiative aiming at “providing harmonised terminology and methods, as well as practical guidelines and results allowing the intercomparison of continental or global Digital Elevation Models (DEM)” [4]. DEMIX has been divided into three subgroups, focused on the “Terminology and analytical basis” (subgroup 1, or SG1), “Algorithms and software” (SG2) and “Platforms and processing” (SG3). A fundamental work of DEMIX SG1 has provided a terminology and definitions for DEM products [1]. Works of DEMIX SG2 resulted in the creation of a DEM ranking framework, based on the Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) methodology [5]. Given a set of DEMIX tiles [6] ($\approx 10 \times 10 \text{ km}$ areas), DEMs and criteria (defined and/or implemented by the user), this methodology allows to rank the DEMs with potential ties. Finally, works of DEMIX SG3 focused on DEM quality assessments (LiDAR or VHR DEM reference data) [7] and transformation studies (resampling methods, projections, datum changes), DEM planimetric misregistration assessment methodology [8] and the development of free DEM processing and visualisation platforms [9].

IV. DEMIX SG3 – PLATFORMS AND PROCESSING

The works performed in DEMIX SG3 are primarily meant to open the DEMIX methodology (defined by SG2) to a wider audience, through the development of dedicated free tools and web applications. These developments would not be possible without the support of preliminary studies focused on DEM validation and transformation methods, which are presented hereafter.

A. Global DEMs vs. LiDAR datasets

Since 2020, the DEMIX SG3 working group has carried out several DEM studies, beginning with the assessment of global DEMs (ASTER GDEM, ALOS World 3D, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 and SRTMGL1) from global reference LiDAR datasets (ICESat-1, ICESat-2 and GEDI) [10]. The assessments have shown the superiority of Copernicus DEM GLO-30 over the three other global DEMs, either in terms of product quality (with regards to the EDAP guidelines) or in a quasi-global statistical comparison from 59 319 279 ICESat-1 elevation measurements (see Fig.1 for histograms). With regards to this reference data, Copernicus DEM GLO-30 has shown an elevation difference RMSE of 0.628 m, followed by ALOS World 3D (1.660 m), SRTMGL1 (2.554 m) and finally ASTER GDEM (7.911 m). In a subsequent study, Copernicus DEMs (EEA-10, GLO-30 and GLO-90) were compared to the ICESat-2 and GEDI LiDAR products. Copernicus DEM GLO-30 has shown low elevation errors with regards to ICESat-2 terrain (0.999 m), followed by the top of canopy (2.907 m). Higher errors were found with GEDI lowest mode (3.431 m) and highest return (6.603 m) measurements. While Copernicus DEM GLO-30 is statistically better than other DEMs at a global scale, thematic applications can still benefit from other DEMs, such as ALOS World 3D showcasing more roughness than Copernicus DEMs in the Afar Triangle (Mount Musa Ali Terara and region of Balho, west of Randa). The spaceborne LiDAR datasets used in this study are adequate for global assessments, but may be too sparse for very specific study areas. Local LiDAR

Figure 1. DEMs vs. LiDAR elevation difference histograms (-3m to +3m).

campaigns and their derived Very High-Resolution (VHR) DEMs perfectly fit this purpose.

B. VHR DEMs studies

In recent years, many airborne LiDAR campaigns were carried out, resulting in Very High-Resolution (VHR) DEMs of cities, regions and countries of the world. Many of these DEMs are now public, with very permissive licenses. Several of these VHR DEMs were integrated into VtWeb [11] and the DEMIX Operations Platform [12], free web applications allowing the visualisation and processing of DEMs (further discussed in section E). These integrations required to find crucial DEM metadata (licenses and access rights, resolution, spatial and temporal extent, horizontal and vertical datums, projection with associated coordinates systems, point or area pixel type...) to bring these models into the WGS84 datum and EGM2008 geoid. In most cases, this information is either difficult to find or poorly documented. This problem motivated the creation of a continuously maintained DEM metadata table [13], gathering all the information required to use and intercompare DEMs. Despite this fundamental work, the transformations required to express these DEMs in international datums and common projections can still be difficult to perform for end users. Consequently, further SG3 studies have been carried out on this issue, with the goal of creating free automatic tools to perform this task.

C. Datums, projection changes and resampling

Most global DEMs are referenced to international horizontal datums (e.g. WGS84 or ITRS) and vertical datums (e.g., EGM96 or EGM2008), in an equirectangular projection (or “geographic” CRS). In these cases, DEM comparisons are relatively simple, consisting of resampling one DEM to be superimposable with the second one, and, if necessary, performing a vertical reference system change by using geoid height grids. However, most of the local VHR DEMs have a proper datum and projection showing non-negligible differences with these international systems. Studies performed to resample VHR DEMs to these international datums highlighted the most important metadata to be retrieved, which are the horizontal datum (including name and realization), the projection (and associated coordinate reference system), and the vertical datum (usually, a geoid model which is released as a grid of heights, often above WGS84). Additionally, a transformation method (and potentially parameters) is necessary to convert coordinates from a local datum to a continental or international one. Most datum transformations operate on geocentric coordinates (e.g., NAD83 to ITRS realizations [14]), but transformations on geodetic or projected coordinates also exist (e.g., the OSTN15 model of UK and Ireland [15]). The accurate superimposition of DEMs also depends on the resampling methods. For DEMs, interpolation methods (e.g., nearest neighbour, bilinear, bicubic) are typically used to increase the

number of elevation samples (smaller GSD), whereas aggregation methods (e.g., mean or gaussian weighted) are used to lower the number of samples (higher GSD). Studies carried out by SG3 highlighted the impact of interpolation methods on DEM elevations and derived layers. These studies show that the bicubic interpolation is the most suitable for the resampling of DEMs, as its “edge enhancement” can be parameterized to preserve features of interest (elevations, slopes, curvatures). Consequently, this interpolation has been chosen for studies regarding the assessment of planimetric shifts between DEMs.

D. Planimetric Misregistration Assessment

Planimetric displacements of features (e.g., crests, thalwegs, shores, trees, buildings) can be observed from one DEM to another. These misalignments are an important source of biases in DEM comparison studies, as they have a direct impact on the elevation differences (see Fig.2). Members of the DEMIX SG3 have defined a new methodology allowing to estimate sub-pixel displacement between two DEMs sharing the same geometry [8] (i.e., on the same grid of pixels) based on the disparity analysis algorithm. Using this method, a displacement vector field is retrieved, allowing to visualise systematic errors (vectors of same direction and length) or local anomalies. The methodology has shown to retrieve artificial planimetric displacements at a sub pixel level, with an error ranging from 12 to 20% of the pixel size. These accuracies can be further improved by increasing the “context” of the algorithm (precisely, the correlation window size) with an additional computation cost. As many comparison methods, the algorithm requires both input DEMs to be sampled over the same grid. Further studies have been performed to retrieve the best resampling method for this purpose, based on several bicubic interpolations with different slope values (increasing or decreasing the sharpness of the output image). The study shows that the best bicubic (BBC) slope parameter is dependent on the study area, and shows a logarithmic correlation coefficient of 0.717 with regards to terrain roughness.

E. DEM visualisation and processing tools

The knowledge acquired from these studies allowed to develop and maintain free and easy to use DEM visualisation and processing tools. The VtWeb [11] platform allows the multi-scale

Figure 2. Effects of planimetric shifts - EU-DEM vs. EEA-10 over Malta.

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on-the-fly processing and visualisation of EO data. Several global DEMs and VHR local DEMs of Brazil, England, France, Italy, Uruguay and Wales have been integrated into VtWeb. Using the Processing On-the-Fly Macro-Language (POF-ML), users are able to display elevations in a chosen range, apply colormaps, compute DEM elevation differences or derived layers such as slope norms, slope azimuths and curvatures. DEM integrations are generally followed by the edition of hyperlook documents reporting the main features and defects of the integrated DEM, to display the differences between two DEMs [16] or to highlight the difference between the successive versions of a same DEM [17]. These documents are enriched with “hyperlook” links, allowing to retrieve interactive views of DEMs on the VtWeb platform. Additionally, two plugins have been developed to interpolate profiles on DEM elevations and to visualise VtWeb layers directly into QGIS. In parallel of these developments, the DEMIX Jupyter Notebook [18] and the DEMIX Operations Platform [12] were developed to download VHR and global DEMIX tiles, and to ease the access to the DEMIX methodology and DEM processing. The DEMIX Jupyter Notebook is oriented toward scientists, allowing to retrieve DEM elevations and compute criteria over user defined DEMIX tiles (areas of approximately 10x10km) by writing a few lines of Python code. Complementarily, the DEMIX Operations Platform provides access to these functions with a simpler user interface and easy-to-use functionalities (DEM ranking and GeoTIFF exports).

V. CONCLUSION

In continuation of the fundamental works of DEMIX SG1 and SG2, the studies performed by SG3 tackled important aspects of DEM comparisons, from transformations (resampling, projections and datum changes) to validation methods (assessments from LiDAR datasets, planimetric misregistrations assessment). Results of these studies were applied to the development of free tools allowing the access to DEMs and the DEMIX methodology to a wide audience. Additionally, the extensive work on VHR DEMs allowed the definition of EDAP standard guidelines dedicated to DEM products. With the increasing availability of these local DEMs expressed in various geometries, the work of DEMIX SG3 remains crucial up to this date. Ongoing works on aggregation methods, future works on cross-border merging algorithms and future DEM integrations could pave the way to a future multi-scale and multi-source DEMs, created from the seamless and dynamic processing of a wide variety of local and global DEMs.

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